

"MEDICAL ASSISTANT" IS A MICRO PARADIGM OF COMMON-SENSE UNITS IN MEDICINE

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Abstract. *The article presents the concept of the micro-paradigm of the common-sense units "Medical Assistant", "assistant", "nurse", "medical doctor/nurse", "paramedic", "midwife" and the researches of scientists.*

Keywords: *assistant, medical doctor/nurse, paramedic, midwife, hospital worker, cancer, flu etc.*

INTRODUCTION

Personal names related to medicine with the common symbol "assistant" are a minority. They are: nurse, nurse/male nurse, paramedic, midwife. According to the "Etymological dictionary of the Uzbek language", the word "nurse" originally meant "women who nursed the same mother in relation to each other", and later it was used to express the meanings of "sister", "hospital worker" (O'TEL-3, p. 278). From this explanation, it is known that the lexeme nurse first embodied the concepts of "collaborative woman", then "sister" and "hospital worker". Today, the terms nurse and medical nurse mean "a specialist woman with secondary education working under the supervision of a doctor in treatment-prophylaxis or children's institutions". In English, this lexeme is equivalent to the word "nurse" and embodies the following themes.

The component analysis of the lexemes "nurse" and "nurse" shows that among their themes, the themes "woman" and "medical assistant" are common to both, and the rest are different. Also, in terms of the number of senses, it became known that the English people describe more expressions with this word compared to the Uzbek people.

In the Uzbek language, the word "nurse" is the only term for women, but the form of reference for men is controversial. Although the explanation of the word "nurse" is explained in the "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" by A. Madvaliev and the description of the origin is explained in the "Etymological Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" by Sh. Rakhmatullaev, its male application form is not mentioned in these sources. It follows that these terminologists have not yet come to a final solution.

In addition, the words "medbrat" and "medical doctor" are also used in the general lexicon of the Uzbek language, and they are also considered as such units. The lexeme Medbrat is actually borrowed from the Russian language and is used only in oral and informal speech; its translation into Uzbek - doctor of medicine can be widely used in official speech: German doctor of medicine (Medbrat) Nils Hegel is suspected of murdering 84 patients.

In A. Kasimov's "explanatory dictionary of medical terms", it is preferable to call the form of reference of the term "nurse" to a man as "nurse":

Nurse. A specialist employee with secondary special education working under the supervision of a doctor in treatment-prophylactic or children's institutions - male.

In our opinion, this opinion is the most acceptable. After all, in most cases, words with the suffix "-a" for the female gender, and without the suffix for the male gender, are universally understood in order to express gender signs in the Uzbek language. For example, a scientist is a scientist, a teacher is a teacher. This variety, which has arisen within units of the same meaning,

causes many difficulties for translators, linguists and speakers. Since there is a gender sign in the lexeme nurse, we believe that a form of reference should also be created in it for the representative of the opposite sex. After all the scientists come to a consensus on this matter, it is necessary to make some changes to the name of the field of specialization - "Higher Nursing". After all, representatives of both sexes are trained equally in this direction. In our opinion, it should be called "Higher Nursing (Nursing) Work". In modern English linguistics, the term nurse belongs to the neutral gender and does not choose a gender in its use:

Actually, most of the people around the world use the term «Nurse» to address both male and female nurses¹. (In fact, most people in the world use the term nurse to refer to both male and female nurses.)

It follows that unlike its conditional equivalent in Uzbek, the lexeme nurse in English also has the meaning of "man". In order to clearly express the gender, the words "female" and "male" can be used in front of it:

A female client may be embarrassed by a male nurse performing personal care procedures². (A female client may be embarrassed by a (male) nurse's personal treatment.)

It is clear from the above that today the associative meaning of the lexeme "nurse" in Uzbek is "woman", and in English - "woman" and "man". Terminologists are still debating how to find a masculine version of this unit in the Uzbek language. After all, it is not easy to find a common, alternative option for common language and scientific terminology. For this reason, at the same time, the synonymy of this term is expanding.

Another associative-thematic field is the term paramedic. A paramedic is often thought of as a male medical worker. But this term is universal and can be used for both female and male medical personnel:

Paramedic. A medical worker with secondary specialized medical education who works independently or under the supervision of a doctor.

Paramedic lexeme differs from other units with the term "assistant" with the terms "paramedic and emergency medical care provider", "diagnoser", "birth attendant (paramedic-midwife)". The English equivalent of this term is paramedic, which is no different from its Uzbek form.

Modern scientific linguists and terminologists avoid choosing words that express gender and race when choosing or creating a new term. This situation is mostly observed in names of persons related to international medicine. But we cannot say the same about the terms (midwife, nurse) that our people have been using for a long time. For example, in our national worldview, a midwife is imagined only as a woman. Because in history midwives consisted of only women. For this reason, in the "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" the midwife lexeme is explained as follows:

Midwife. A woman who gives birth to pregnant women. A woman raising babies (O'TIL-1, p. 650).

The English form of this lexeme - midwife (mid - in old English, wife - wife) means "with a woman"¹. It can be seen that in ancient times the British used this word only to refer to women. But since the end of the 20th century, it has been applied to both sexes. It is known that the patient, as a medical concept, means "a person whose normal state of the organism is disturbed" and is synonymous with the words "sick" and "ill":

One night the patient suffered greatly. (A. Qahhor, Patient)

At the same time, it serves to express the meaning of "love, person suffering from love, lover" in the artistic style:

The patient is relieved of his pain,
I don't know where to go. (Mashrab, Devon)

This sign is not observed in the English alternative patient, it only expresses the medical meaning: This will not serve as a hospital, but instead will be like a patient's temporary home (J. Robert, Daily cases top 3000 for the first time).

(It serves as a temporary shelter for patients, not as a hospital.)

The fact that the concept of "patient" has more connotations in Uzbek than in English defines another unique aspect of our native language.

The patient mesoparadigm consists of the following medical terms: Inpatient: In any case, an inpatient spends most of his time in a place (Hi, p. 117); On Friday, the state reported total inpatient capacity in Ohio hospitals is at about 73%, with ICU beds at about 80% (E. Bamforth, Ohio reports 10,359 daily change in coronavirus cases, 128 deaths: Friday update).

Outpatient: Outpatients are sent home after 1-1.5 hours of examination, when their general mood is good; Even seven months later, there are still shortages of PPE like masks, gloves, and face-shields with increasing demand coming from non-hospital facilities such as nursing homes, homeless shelters, outpatient clinics and schools (J. Faust, Ok, you've just won the election. Now fix covid). Inpatient and ambulatory patients are medically different concepts and have different meanings in relation to the place of direct treatment. For example, "hospital", "clinic" for an inpatient; and for the lexeme of an ambulatory patient, such terms as "house", "polyclinic" are typical. So, from a social point of view, although the word patient is considered a single concept, it can serve as a component of a joint term in the medical discourse and have additional special meanings.

Also, depending on the disease, the patient lexeme can appear in a sentence in a different way. For example, in Uzbek, a patient with the flu calls himself "I am flu", a patient diagnosed with cancer - "men rakman", and a patient diagnosed with diabetes "I am sugar" are common in the national lexicon observed. That is, although the word patient is omitted in oral speech, the meaning of "patient" is understood as a person suffering from a certain disease. But this condition is observed only with the names of some medical diseases. It would be a mistake if we translate the words "I am sick/I am sick" into English by omitting the Uzbek word, such as "I am flu", "I am cancer", "I am diabetes". In the English expression of these sentences, it is understood that the person himself as an object is a disease of influenza, cancer and diabetes. The rules of the English lexical and grammatical system prevent this. From the above lexical and grammatical differences, it is known that in oral and informal speech, the Uzbek people strive for brevity in cases related to the concept of "patient". This aspect revealed the unique linguo-pragmatic nature of units with the term "patient" in the Uzbek medical terminological system:

In addition, such units were identified among medical terms that combine the concepts of "disease name" and "patient" and are expressed in speech as a single term. These terms are made by the "disease name + morpheme" method.

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